

THE INFLUENCE OF FREE EDGES ON CURVED BEAM STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

Large aerospace parts are typically certified by testing narrow specimens, such as curved laminates, which have exposed free edges. These edges are found to reduce curved laminate strength by 22%, meaning this method is conservative. The free edges also create a singularity, such that Finite Element modelling is challenging, which is typically addressed using non-linear analysis. A new treatment is developed whereby a thin layer of resin is applied to the free edges of curved laminates. This significantly reduces the edge effect and delays the initiation of failure. This paper shows that the resin edge treatment increases the strength of curve laminate test specimens by 17%. The treatment also simplifies FE modelling by allowing for non-zero stresses normal to the laminate edge, which removes the singularity. This enables the use of linear FE models, which now converge at the laminate edge. A linear FE method developed in this paper predicts the strength of treated curved laminates to within 7.5% of the test values.

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

CBS	=	Curved beam strength – required moment per unit width for failure.
CFRP	=	Carbon fibre reinforced plastic.
FE	=	Finite Element.
LHS	=	Left hand side.
UD	=	Uni-directional.
UTS	=	Ultimate tensile strength.

Symbols

D	=	Roller diameter.
d_x	=	Horizontal distance between centre of adjacent upper and lower roller.
d_y	=	Vertical distance between centre of adjacent upper and lower roller.
i, j	=	Local directional parameters with 1 and 2 in-plane and 3 out-of-plane.
P	=	Applied load.
Φ	=	Angle between limbs of curved laminate and horizontal.
s_{ii}, s_{ij}	=	Material allowable.
σ_{ii}	=	Direct stress.
t	=	Thickness of curved laminate.
τ_{ij}	=	Shear stress.
w	=	Width of curved laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

The qualification of aerospace parts and structures is typically validated with a programme of testing. Thousands of tests are carried out on the smallest scale, with fewer and fewer carried out as the test parts get larger and more complex. It is important that at every scale the test is representative of the final product. The response of curved laminates to out-of-plane loading can be assessed by conducting a 4-point bend test [1]. These tests are typically carried out on small curve laminate specimens, several orders of magnitude narrower than the final product. For UD CFRP material, considered in this paper, bending tests induce high inter-laminar stresses at the free edges of such narrow specimens, generated by the mismatch in mechanical properties between plies with different fibre orientations. This edge-effect generally causes narrow specimens to fail at a significantly lower load than would be predicted by 2D, plane strain analysis. It also results in the narrow specimen not being representative of the final product, where the final product is very wide and/or is built into surrounding structure at its ends, such that it has no free edges. Evaluating the edge effect is challenging and many analytical and numerical methods have been proposed. Literature surveys of these can be found in review articles [2-3]. There are no analytical methods at present that calculate the exact stresses at the free edge. Linear FE analysis often results in highly localised stresses near the free edge that are higher than the strength of the material. A method for assessing when these high stresses will lead to failure has been developed using linear elastic fracture mechanics [4]. Non-linear FE analysis is often performed in order to capture failure initiation and predict composite laminate strength, such as a 3D non-linear FE model for delamination damage onset and growth in composite spar wingskin joints [5].

In this paper a number of physical 4-point bend tests have been carried out alongside linear FE analysis to investigate the behaviour of the specimens. In this way the edge effect is established as well as the convergence of the FE models. Thereafter a resin edge treatment designed to protect the free edges is developed and explored in order to reduce the edge effect. A diagram of the curved laminates is shown in Fig. 1, illustrating the free edges and resin edge treatment. The curved beam strength (CBS) is used as a metric for quantitatively assessing and comparing the strength of the curved elements. CBS is defined as the applied bending moment per unit width (or running moment) at failure.

Figure 1 Curved laminates without and with resin edge treatment, showing the free edge in the untreated sample and how this is protected by resin for the treated sample. The axes show the direction of fibres in 0° plies (1) and 90° plies (2). Dimensions in mm, not to scale.

2 TEST METHODOLOGY

2.1 Rig Design and CBS Calculation

The CBS of curved laminate specimens was assessed by means of a 4-point bend test. The test setup was adapted from ASTM D6415 [1]. An unfolding moment was generated by 4 rollers attached to a test rig, as shown schematically in Fig. 2. Well lubricated smooth steel rollers were used in order to ensure they rotated freely within their housing and could not transfer load into the coupon via shear, which would invalidate many of the modelling assumptions. The displacement of the upper two rollers

was controlled by an Instron machine at a rate of 1 mm/min. By monitoring the load and displacement, the applied moment, and hence CBS, was calculated from [1] according to

$$CBS = \left(\frac{P}{2w \cos \Phi} \right) \left(\frac{d_x}{\cos \Phi} + (D + t) \tan \Phi \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\Phi = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{-d_x(D + t) + d_y \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2 - D^2 - 2Dt - t^2}}{d_x^2 + d_y^2} \right), \quad (2)$$

where w and t are, respectively, the width and thickness of the specimen and D is the roller diameter. All other parameters are defined according to Fig. 2. Note that d_y and hence Φ changes during the test as the upper rollers displace downwards. The values at failure were taken to calculate CBS. The selection of d_x was as small as possible to minimise vertical displacement to failure (and hence geometrical non-linearity), without being so small as to induce failure by shear in the limbs.

Figure 2 Schematic of test setup in cross-section. All dimensions in mm.

2.2 Specimen Preparation

A large C-section structure was manufactured from M21/IMA uni-directional CFRP material. Using an AFP machine 39 plies were laid up, with final cure in an autoclave. The total thickness of the laminate was approximately 10 mm. The laminate consisted of the symmetric sequence of fibre angles $[\mp 45, 90, 0, \mp 45, 90, 0, \mp 45_2, 90, \mp 45, 90, 0, \mp 45, 0, \pm 45, 0, 90, \pm 45, 90, \pm 45_2, 0, 90, \pm 45, 0, 90, \pm 45]$, where 90° fibres wrap around the corner, along the axis labelled 2 in Fig. 1. Curved laminate specimens were then cut from the C-section according to the dimensions in Fig. 2, with a nominal width of 52 mm. The free edges were then finely polished to avoid exacerbating the edge effect and the final width was measured after the final grinding process was complete.

2.3 Resin Edge Treatment

Treatment was applied to the free edges of a number of the specimens. After the edges had been polished they were plasma treated, in order to ensure the highest quality bond possible, and then the resin (EP1330LV, supplied by Resinlab) was applied. Approximately 3 mm of resin was applied to each free edge, increasing the overall specimen width to approximately 58 mm, as shown in Fig. 1. However, for the purposes of calculating CBS according to Eq. 1, the width was taken as that of the CFRP only.

3 TEST RESULTS

Each test was stopped immediately after the first failure event occurred, identified by either an audible crack or load drop. The specimen was then inspected visually, using a microscope and CT scanner to identify the location of first failure. A summary of the test results is shown in Table 1.

Sample	Edge treatment	CBS (kNmm/mm)	Average CBS
A-1	None	7.56	7.38
A-2	None	7.19	
B-1	Resin	8.70	8.65
B-2	Resin	8.60	
B-3	Resin	8.66	

Table 1 Test results for curved laminate specimens without and with resin edge treatment, showing an increase in CBS of 17% for the average test result of the treated specimens.

From Table 1 it can be seen that the specimens that had resin edge treatment consistently achieved a higher CBS than those without treatment, with an average CBS increase of 17%. The failure location of the test specimens was found to be relatively predictable, with a clear difference between specimens that were resin edge treated and those that were not. The specimens generally failed with multiple delamination simultaneously (see Fig. 3 and Fig. 4), meaning it was not possible to determine where failure first occurred from test data alone. However, the untreated specimens both failed within the inner half of the laminate only. Figure 3 shows Sample A-1 but A-2 also failed in a very similar manner. In contrast, the edge treated specimens all exhibited large delaminations throughout the thickness of the laminate. Figure 4 shows Sample B-1 as an example but B-2 and B-3 also exhibited similar failure behaviour. At the point of failure during the test, the resin edge shattered, leaving the free edge of the CFRP exposed, as shown in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, for either side of Sample B-1. B-2 and B-3 exhibited this behaviour as well.

Figure 3 Post-test CT scan cross-section of Sample A-1, without resin edge treatment. Failure locations are within the inner half of the laminate only (towards the inner radius).

Figure 4 Post-test CT scan of Sample B-1, with resin edge treatment, cross-sectioned within the CFRP. Failure locations are seen throughout the laminate thickness, in contrast with the untreated specimen.

Figure 5 Post-test CT scans of Sample B-1, which had resin edge treatment, showing each edge.

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Finite Element modelling was conducted using ABAQUS software [6]. In the model, the curved laminates were assumed to have the nominal width of 52 mm. The plies were assumed to have a thickness of 0.24 mm, with a 0.015 mm interface layer of pure resin between each ply. The assumed mechanical properties for both the fibrous ply material and the resin rich interface material are given in Table 2, assuming the same ratio between s_{33} and s_{13} for M21/IMA [7] as for 8552/AS4 [8] (for which both are quoted). The assumed material properties for the resin edge material of the treated curved elements are also shown in Table 2.

Orthotropic fibrous layer		Isotropic interface layer		Resin edge material	
E_{11}	135 GPa	E	8.5 GPa	E	8.9 GPa
E_{22}, E_{33}	8.5 GPa	ν	0.35	ν	0.35
G_{12}, G_{13}	4.0 GPa				
G_{23}	3.5 GPa	M21/IMA allowables		Resin edge allowable	
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.35	s_{33}	60 MPa	UTS	55 MPa
ν_{23}	0.5	s_{13}	97 MPa		

Table 2 Assumed mechanical properties for resin edge material (EP1330LV) and CFRP material (M21/IMA), where 1 is the fibre direction in-plane, 2 is perpendicular to the fibre direction in-plane and 3 is out-of-plane. s_{33} is the direct through-thickness strength and s_{13} is the transverse shear strength according to HEXCEL [7-8].

Modelling the full 3D bending test with rollers and contact analysis would be extremely computationally expensive. Therefore a simplified model was used. Curved laminates were modelled with shortened limbs. A moment was applied to the end of one limb using a beam multi-point constraint (MPC), with all degrees of freedom fixed at the end of the opposite limb. Whilst this does not accurately model stresses in the limbs, it gives the same stress field towards the apex of the curved section as a full model with rollers. In this region there is a resulting moment caused by the roller displacement. Since this is the critical region where failure occurs during the tests, it is believed that the simplified model is suitable for modelling the stress field and predicting CBS.

4.1 Mesh refinement and model parameters

Standard linear hexahedral elements are used throughout the model with reduced integration (C3D8R). Stresses change most rapidly in the vicinity of the free edge and this is also the key area of interest for failure initiation. Therefore, the FE mesh is graded such that there is higher fidelity near the edge than towards the mid-width. The fibrous layers are modelled with 6 elements through thickness, graded such that the outer elements are smaller than those in the middle of the layers. The interface layers are modelled with 2 elements through thickness. Around the curved section there are 50 elements, without grading and down each limb 5 elements, again without grading. The grading is achieved using the double bias option in the mesh seeding tool of ABAQUS. The number of elements along a line is set, together with the bias ratio, which determines the approximate ratio between the smallest and largest element. An example of this is illustrated in Fig. 6. A summary of all the mesh seeding is contained within Table 3.

Figure 6 Line separated into 7 elements with double bias ratio of 8, meaning the middle element is 8 times larger than the outer most elements, with adjacent elements scaling by a factor of 2.

		No. elements	Bias ratio
Across width		40	544
Through thickness	Fibrous layer	6	3
	Interface layer	2	-
Around curved section		50	-
Down each limb		5	-

Table 3 Summary of mesh seeding for FE model of curved laminate. Note that the number of elements and bias ratio across the width was varied as part of reliability and singularity studies in 5.1.1 and 6.2 respectively.

5 FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS

5.1 Untreated curved laminate

The stresses away from the free edges can be accurately modelled by simple analytical methods using a plane strain assumption. Close to the edges, however, this assumption does not hold and the stresses become highly complex, under the influence of a numerical singularity at the free edges. For example, there is a sharp rise near the edge in direct through thickness stress, σ_{33} , as illustrated in Fig. 7. This behaviour is caused physically by the discontinuity at the free edge and the differential strain of 0° , 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ layers. Similar behaviour is observed in through thickness shear stresses, τ_{13} and τ_{23} , within the interface layers.

Figure 7 a) Curved laminate sectioned at the apex of the corner. Maximum tensile σ_{33} stress occurs at the edge of the 36th ply (4th from inner radius). b) Plot of σ_{33} across the width of the 36th ply, with values normalised relative to the mid-width value. Near the free edges there is a sharp rise in σ_{33} stress in order to compensate for stresses normal to the free edge reducing to zero at the free edge.

From Fig. 7, it is clear that analysing stresses at the mid-width, or by using plane strain assumptions, would grossly over predict the performance of curved laminate specimens. Stresses must be assessed close to the edge, where failure is likely to initiate, in order to accurately predict CBS.

5.1.1 Reliability of model

The presence of a free edge creates a singularity in the Finite Element model, which significantly affects stress results obtained for the elements closest to the edge. Generally the first 2 elements adjacent to the free edge give unreliable results. Thereafter the effect of the free edge singularity rapidly dissipates, as evident in Fig. 7b. A number of mesh refinements have been made to the curved laminate model in order to investigate the effect of the singularity and determine when the predicted stress field can be considered reliable.

Stresses were analysed at fixed physical distances away from the free edge. With different mesh refinements this physical distance could be represented by any number of elements. It was found that meshes that included 4 or more elements within the set distance showed negligible difference in their results and were therefore assumed to have converged. Meshes with 3 elements within the distance gave a marginally different result and those with just 1 or 2 elements produced significantly different results. It was therefore determined that stresses should only be analysed at least 4 elements away from the free edge in order to give reliable results and that stresses would never converge at the free edge as the mesh was refined.

5.1.2 Predicted CBS and failure location

The stresses near the free edge are complex and involve inter-laminar shear and direct stress. Therefore a mixed mode failure criterion is more suitable than a maximum stress criterion. The strength of the laminates was assessed using a quadratic damage onset criterion, defined by Camanho et al [9] as

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}^+}{S_{33}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{13}}\right)^2} = 1 \quad , \quad (3)$$

where σ_{33}^+ refers to positive values of direct inter-laminar stress only, since compressive stress is not assumed to contribute to the onset of delamination. When the left hand side of Eq. 3 ≥ 1 , failure is predicted. Using the final mesh, refined as previously described in Table 3, stresses were analysed 4 elements away from the free edge, at a physical distance of 95 μm , as it was found this distance gave a close prediction for CBS to that of the average test result. Figure 8 shows the result of Eq. 3 through the thickness at this distance from the free edge on the apex of the corner. This was produced from the FE result with an applied running moment of 7.04 kNmm/mm. At this value failure is first predicted near the inner radius between plies 36 and 37.

Figure 8 Through thickness failure criterion (LHS Eq. 3) evaluated 4 elements away from the free edge (width-wise). Applied running moment is 7.04 kNmm/mm.

5.2 Treated curved laminate

For the central CFRP section of the model, an identical mesh was used as for the untreated curved laminates. The mesh in the resin edges applied to the free edges was set to achieve comparable size elements at the resin edge-CFRP interface as on the CFRP side of the interface. Stresses were assessed 4 elements (95 μm) away from the resin edge-CFRP interface to be consistent with the untreated model. Fig. 9 shows the result of Eq. 3 through the thickness at this location. With an applied running moment of 12.8 kNmm/mm, failure is predicted almost simultaneously close to inner radius (between plies 38-39) and towards the outer radius (plies 4-6). This is significantly higher than the average test CBS, however reasons for this and an alternative method for assessing the strength of treated laminates are developed in the following discussion.

Figure 9 Through thickness failure criterion evaluated 4 elements away from the resin edge interface. Applied running moment is 12.8 kNmm/mm.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Comparison of test and FE results

Failure criteria	CBS (kNmm/mm)	
	No treatment	Resin edge treatment
Test average	7.38 (ply 18-37)	8.65 (ply 1-37)
Plane strain	9.51 (ply 23-24)	
FE σ_{33}^+	7.16 (ply 36)	21.5 (ply 18-19)
FE τ_{13}	10.2 (ply 4-5)	13.6 (ply 4-5)
FE Camanho	7.04 (ply 36-37)	12.8 (ply 4-6, 38-39)
FE Camanho*	Un-converged	8.00* (ply 38-39)

Table 4 Comparison between test results, plane strain and 3D FEA for curved laminates without and with resin edge treatment. Ply or interface location of failure is indicated in brackets. FE results based upon stresses 4 elements (95 μ m) away from the edge, apart from *, which is assessed using the converged values of stress at the CFRP edge.

Table 4 contains a summary of the test results and FEA prediction for curved laminate CBS. The FE prediction for the untreated specimen is in close agreement with the test result, under-predicting strength by 5%, allowing for some conservatism. The free edge appears to have reduced strength by 22%, by comparing the untreated test average with CBS based on plane strain analysis. The FE for the treated specimen over-predicts test strength by 57%, assuming failure first occurs in the CFRP section of the specimen according to Camanho failure criterion 95 μ m away from the edge. However, using the converged values of stress at the edge (discussed in 6.2) it is possible to get a prediction much closer to the test result, as per the last value in Table 4.

6.2 Analysis of the free edge singularity

The singularity caused by the free edge makes FE modelling of the untreated curved laminates extremely challenging. In order to illustrate the effect, the plot in Fig. 10 has been generated by varying the mesh seeding across the width of the laminate (described previously in 4.1). The direct inter-laminar stress was measured one element away from the CFRP edge in the middle of the 36th ply, which is the 0° ply closest to the inner radius and is where maximum tensile σ_{33} is seen close to the CFRP edge. Note that the CFRP edge is the free edge for the untreated curved laminates and the boundary with the resin edge for the treated ones. By varying the width-wise mesh refinement, the size of the element at this edge was varied, as was the physical distance from the edge where stresses were being taken.

Figure 10 Direct inter-laminar stress in fourth ply from inner radius, one element away from the CFRP edge for varying mesh refinements (width-wise). The untreated average test CBS of 7.38 kNmm/mm was applied. The σ_{33} allowable is also shown.

From Fig. 7 it appears that the untreated curved laminate stress value is tending towards infinity as it is measured closer to the free edge. This is because there can be no stress normal to the free edge. Other stresses, such as direct inter-laminar stress, become very large near the edge and infinite at the edge in order to compensate for this. In contrast, the treated curved laminate stress value converges to a finite value. This is because the presence of the resin edge allows for some stress normal to the CFRP edge, in turn preventing other stresses from becoming infinite. The result is that it is much more feasible to model the treated laminates than the untreated ones. For a given allowable for σ_{33} for example, almost any CBS could be predicted for an untreated laminate dependent on how far from the free edge stress is evaluated. Therefore measuring stresses at some distance from the free edge gives close agreement with test results, i.e. the point at which the free edge FEA crosses the allowable in Fig. 10. However, this is not useful without a reliable method for determining how far from the free edge to evaluate stresses, based upon known parameters about the specimen and test setup. In contrast, finding the value of stress the treated model converges to at the CFRP edge is more repeatable. Using the convergence values for the model of the treated curved laminate, a CBS of 8.00 kNmm/mm is predicted, based on Camanho failure criterion, plotted in Fig. 11. This is approximately 7.5% lower than the average test value.

Figure 11 Through thickness failure criterion using the finest mesh for the treated laminate model, which appears close to convergence according to Fig. 10. Applied running moment is 8.00 kNm/mm.

Although the analysis in Fig. 11 gives a CBS prediction close to that of the treated test results, the failure location predicted (at the interface layer closest to the inner radius) is not observed in the tests (see Fig. 4). In order to investigate this discrepancy, the FE model was setup with an applied running moment equal to the average treated test CBS of 8.65 kNm/mm. It was found that the tensile stresses in the resin edge caused by bending peaked at 60 MPa. The EP1330LV datasheet quotes a UTS of 55 MPa. This would indicate that failure of the applied resin edge treatment is likely to have occurred. During the test it was observed that the resin edge shattered into many pieces, as well as multiple delaminations appearing in the CFRP, all within a fraction of a second. It was not possible to determine exactly which failure occurred first. If the resin edge fails, CFRP edge protection is lost and therefore the laminate is likely to fail simultaneously. Moreover, the loss of resin edge protection will affect the stress distribution at the exposed CFRP edge, meaning the failure criterion plot in Fig. 11 would likely change. This could explain why the test does not exhibit failure in the location predicted by the peak in Fig. 11. Another possible explanation for the failure location discrepancy is that the peak in Fig. 11 is dominated by shear stress. While the Camanho failure criterion predicts crack initiation, it may be this is not readily propagated by shear stress. Cracks initiated by tensile inter-laminar stress generally propagate more easily, such as the peak at 9 mm from the outer radius in Fig. 11, where failure is observed in Fig. 4.

7 CONCLUSION

The free edges present in narrow test specimens reduce CBS by 22% as compared with edgeless (or very wide) components according to plane-strain analysis. This compromises the use of narrow test specimens to certify wide structural parts. A new resin edge treatment reduced this edge effect and increases test specimen strength by 17%. Importantly, the addition of resin to the free edges removes the need for stresses normal to the edge to reduce to zero at the edge. This removes the singularity and prevents other stresses becoming infinite at the edge, which allows linear FE models to converge at the laminate edge. This paper shows that, with edge treatment, the initiation of failure can be successfully predicted to within 7.5% using linear FE analysis. The use of linear analysis vastly reduces computation

time as compared with non-linear analysis. Current testing is also conservative for wide parts, whereas the new approach provides confidence in a model-based method for assessing curved laminate strength. This model could be developed to include the effect of manufacturing induced imperfections and show the benefits of alternative laminate designs.

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